

Broadcast Media Content Producers' Perception of the Influence of New Media in Broadcast Production

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Abstract

The advancement in communication technology, which has brought the concept of convergence through the new media, has increased broadcasting activities, audience participation, market competition and other factors. The increase in social networking platforms has brought a diversity of spreading messages, giving avenue to a lot of channels, presenting both opportunities and challenges to broadcast content generators and disseminators. This suggests that new media has greatly transformed gathering, processing and production of broadcast content. It has challenged the way broadcast content is packaged in the mainstream broadcast outfits, changing audience engagement and participation, as well as creating a novel content production opportunities and formats. Therefore, the focus of this study was to appraise broadcast content producers' perception of the challenges and benefits of new media in broadcast production. The study explored the types of new media used by broadcast content producers, the extent of the use of new media in broadcast content production, the importance as well as the limitations of new media technology in broadcast content production. The study made use of the Technological Determinism Theory. The study gathered data from 84 respondents through the employment of the survey design. The study found that new media was highly used by the respondents. The most used new media were social media like Facebook Live (4.7 mean rating and Internet Protocol Television/Over-the-Top-Platforms, 4.7 mean rating). New media has brought efficiency and efficacy in broadcast content production but with some challenges such as high competition for audience attention and adverts, too much of content to handle, and changing audience preferences. It was concluded that despite some challenges with new media in broadcast content production, the news media has presented a huge benefits to broadcast contents producers. The study recommended that both private and public broadcast media owners in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria should increase their budget allocations especially as they concern the purchase of new media equipment and other aspects of production that requires the use of new media technologies such as data subscription.

Keywords: New media, benefits, challenges, broadcast, production

Introduction

The advancement in communication technology, which has brought the concept of convergence through the new media, has increased broadcasting activities, audience participation, market competition and other factors. As a result of this, broadcast content creators and disseminators do take full advantage of new media to reach out to more audience quickly (Kai, 2024). The increase in social networking platforms has brought a diversity of spreading messages, giving avenue to a lot of channels, presenting both opportunities and challenges to broadcast content generators and

disseminators. This suggests that new media has greatly transformed gathering, processing and production of broadcast content. It has challenged the way broadcast content is packaged in the mainstream broadcast outfits, changing audience engagement and participation, as well as creating a novel content production opportunities and formats (Ward, Glancy & Bowman, 2020).

Studies on the impacts and challenges of new media communication technologies on broadcasting have been conducted by researchers across the globe (Chimezie, 2022; Imoh & Ifeanyi, 2023; Kai, 2024; Lucas & Shalgan, 2019; Osapkolor, 2021; Ukwuru, Dudu & Ukwueze, 2024; Wang et al, 2024). In spite of the fact that some of these scholars have skewed their studies to the benefits of new media in broadcast content creation and distribution, there still gap in knowledge. Therefore, the focus of this study is to add to the upsurge of literature by dwelling on the perception of broadcast content producers regarding the challenges and benefits of new media in broadcast production. It focused on broadcasters in some broadcast organisations in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the respondents' extent of the use of new media in broadcast production.
2. To find out the most used types of new media in broadcast production.
3. To assess the benefits of the respondents' use of new media in broadcast production.
4. To find out the challenges of the use of new media in broadcast production.

Review of Literature

Benefits and Challenges of New Media in Broadcast Production

Saka, (2021), supports that ICT has played a meaningful role and function in the strengthening of news production through the years. Osapkolor et al (2021) added that information technology has a significant level of influence on the operations of the media and that the media is now driven by technology which has no turning back. Oscar (2023) in Ukwuru, Dudu and Ukwueze (2023) argue that new media technology has brought significant changes to media production. Wang (2023) concurs that new media has presented a huge opportunity to broadcast news practitioners, giving them a new perspective to video coverage and editing, as well as writing and presentation skills. In the current broadcasting environment, the new media innovation has increased the thinking of broadcast content practitioners, improved content delivery and interaction with listeners and viewers (Pei, 2023).

Scholars have also conducted studies in line with these arguments. For instance, the focus of Ukwuru, Dudu and Ukwueze (2024) study was on exposure and use of new media technologies among broadcasters in South East Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to examine the extent

of exposure and use as well as the dominant new media technologies used by the respondents. The research was supported by technological determinism theory. It utilised the survey design and obtained data from 612 participants. Finding of the investigation indicated that there was a minimal exposure and application of new media technology by broadcasters. The study therefore concluded that the low use of new media technology by the respondents could be attributed to knowledge gap in the application of digital media. The study thus suggested that broadcast stations owners should make available new communication technologies that will improve broadcasting activities in South-East region of Nigeria.

Also, Wekesa, Mberia and Nyakundi (2025) investigated the impact of new media on how broadcasters produce and share content on television. The study collected data through the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods from selected television stations in Kenya. The study utilised the Technological Determinism Theory and Media Determinism Theory. Finding of the study indicated that the most used new media technology included F, X, digital video cameras. YouTube, Live-U, SI media, Zoom apps, OB Tricasters, Skype, Smartphones, among others. The study further found that new media technology has made the production and distribution of television content easier, less expensive and better. Result further revealed the challenges to include fake news and spread of unsubstantiated information. The study concluded that in spite of the challenges, new media technology has made television production faster, efficient and cheaper.

Kai (2024) conducted a study on the use of media in news presentation in broadcast organisations. The study, which made use of the content analysis research approach, established that broadcast content creation and distribution has improved due to the new media communication platforms. These technologies have supported the efficiency and efficacy of broadcast content generation and delivery, enhanced visualised broadcast content presentation, interaction with audience, as well as enhancing personalised broadcast content sensitivity in professional knowledge upgrade. The study concluded that new media communication technologies have brought a lot of convenience to broadcast content creators and distributors.

Further, Chimezie (2022) assessed the application of new media in broadcasting. The study examined the limitations of the use of new media in broadcasting as well as the benefits. The study was anchored on the Technological Determinism Theory. Observation and discussion methods of research were adopted. Finding of the study revealed that CNN and Television Continental made use of new media communication technologies with a view to improving their activities. Nevertheless, data showed that CNN used highly sophisticated new media communication technologies, compared to TVC News. The study's finding further indicated the challenges of new media technologies in broadcasting to include high cost of purchasing the new media tools, maintenance and knowledge gap in catching up with evolving new media technologies. The study, therefore advocated that TVC News step up their new media facilities.

Similarly, the thrust of Olley's (2009) in Chimezie (2024) study was on the impacts of new media on broadcasting in Nigeria. The study also assessed the challenges of the application of new media in the Nigerian broadcasting industry. The study employed the survey research strategy. The finding indicated that while new media was having significant impact on the Nigeria broadcasting

landscape such as improving gathering and dissemination of broadcast contents, it was challenged by high cost of new media gadgets purchase, network issues and electricity challenges.

In the same vein, Lucas and Shalgan (2019) concentrated their research on “Information and Communication Technologies and the Changing Face of News Gathering, Production and Reporting: Highland FM Jos and Plateau Radio and Television Corporation Jos in Focus”. Survey research method was deployed to gather information from the respondents. Technological determinism theory was used to explain the study further. The study found some of the benefits of ICTs in news gathering, production and reporting to include interactivity, immediacy, multimedia, enriching of content, faster and efficient, as well as finding out that most journalists are aware of the use of the ICTs and subsequently embrace them in their news gathering efforts. Furthermore, the study findings revealed that ICTs can be viewed from both an opportunity and a threat to the news industry. The study advocated the need for media establishments to key into the benefits of new media with a view to delivering better and faster content to the audience. In addition, media organisations should send more of their newsroom staff on ICTs training programmes or workshops.

In addition, Imoh and Ifeanyi (2023) assessed the ever changing way of content production and distribution in the new media era. The concern of the study was on the impact of digital technology on the generation, dissemination, and use of broadcast content. Jenkins’ Convergence Theory was adopted. The study gathered data from existing literature. It focused mainly on the benefits and challenges that broadcast content creators encounter in the new media era. The study established that the new media technology has significantly impacted the way broadcast contents are packaged and distributed. It has widened the scope of broadcasting in terms of audience reach and accessibility of broadcast content, giving broadcast content creators to connect with audience across the world. On the other hand, the new media technology has increased competition in the broadcast industry and the challenges of meeting the needs of digital audience based on their individual characteristics. Above all, the study concluded that in the digital space has improved content creation and distribution in the broadcast sector. It recommended that success in the new media broadcast domain depends largely on the ability to embrace new technology, and constantly creating engaging and innovative content.

Shao (2019) assessed the impact of digital media on television and film production. The study employed the content analysis research method. The study established that digital media communication has affected the way film and television contents are produced. It has brought about high quality film and television production. New media communication technology was also changing the way audience members consume film and television content. The study concluded that new media has contributed significantly towards better production of film and television programmes.

Chaudhary et al (2025) studied the impact of new media technology on contemporary media practice. The study, which used qualitative data collection method, found that new media technology has disrupted the conventional media practitioners’ workflows, leading to efficient, fast news production and better audience engagement and participation in media production. The study also found that new media technology has contributed to spread of misinformation and issues

around the quality of news being disseminated. The study recommended that there was the need to adapt to journalistic code of ethics in maintaining integrity and relevance in this increasing digital space.

Wang et al (2024) examined the influence of social communication tools on television content delivery as well as production of film. Findings indicated that social media was reshaping the packaging and distribution of television and film content. This, the study argued, that social media was increasing media consumption due to streaming characteristics of platforms, thus giving viewer different choices. The study recommended that for the television and film content producers to cater to evolving tastes due to the advent of the social media, there was the need for constant innovation in the television and filmmaking landscape.

Theoretical Framework

The study utilised the Technological Determinism Theory. This theory was propounded by in 1982. The theory tries to explain the nexus between people and the adoption and use of technology. Karl Marx further argues that, technological innovations, especially as they concern the media, they serve important roles in human interactions. This implies that, the technology as the present determines how people conduct their affairs. The theory operates on two basic principles. The first principle posits that technological innovations are important in determining how humans conduct their daily activities. The second principle states that changes in technological innovations in a society play key role in modifying changes in society.

Lievrouw and Livingstone (2006) in Odemelam et al. (2024), contend that advancement in technology usually play vital part in determining the type of actions that people take, which is significant to societal transformations. From this position, it is clear that the innovation of new media technology has altered the way information is generated and shared. This is why broadcast content producers have taken advantage of the new media communication technology to enhance their content. The new media technology also provides the broadcast audience the avenue to ask questions from broadcast content producers. This implies the innovation of new media technology has brought a new dimension to broadcast content generation and dissemination. Hence, the relevance of the Technological Determinism Theory to this study.

Methodology

Quantitative research method was adopted for this study. This was considered relevant in the research due to the arguments by experts in quantitative studies that such a design allows for collecting data from large number of sample size and its generalisation characteristics (Creswell, 2009). The study population comprised of broadcast content producers in Nigerian Television Authority, Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (Kapital FM), Berekete Family Radio, African Independent Television (AIT), Channels Television, Cool FM, Hot FM, Wazobia FM, Brila FM, Love FM, Soundcity Television and Silverbird Television, all in Abuja, Nigeria. The researcher selected 7 sample respondents per station, making a total of 84 through the use of availability technique.

Before the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher conducted a pilot test with similar respondents in Keffi to check the reliability of the instrument, and when the responses returned, it showed that questionnaire was appropriate for the data collection. Face-to-face questionnaire distribution method was employed for primary data collection. Descriptive statistics using chart and tables, frequencies, percentages and mean deviation of five-point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), which the criterion mean was put at 3 is accepted result, while 2 is rejected result were used to present the data.

Data Presentation

A total of 84 copies of questionnaire were administered of which 81 were returned and found valid for analysis. Percentage representation is as shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Response Rate Analysis

Figure 2: Respondents’ Extent of the Use of New Media on Broadcast Content Production and Delivery

The level of the use of new media as illustrated in Figure 2 suggests the importance of digital communication technology in the broadcast industry.

Table 1: Responses on the Most Used Types of New Media in Broadcast Production

Option	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean Rating	Decision
Streaming services such as Netflix	37	44	0	0	0	81	4.4	Accepted
Social media like Facebook Live	61	20	0	0	0	81	4.7	Accepted
Podcasting	44	37	0	0	0	81	4.5	Accepted
Internet Protocol Television/Over-the-Top-Platforms	63	18	0	0	0	81	4.7	Accepted

It could be inferred from the data in Table 1 that new media technology has become important to broadcasting.

Table 2: Responses on the Benefits of New Media on Broadcast Content Production and Delivery

Option	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean Rating	Decision
New media presents opportunity to reach a wider audience with ease	55	26	0	0	0	81	4.5	Accepted
It increases audience engagement	70	11	0	0	0	81	4.8	Accepted
New media allows the integration of multimedia services	61	20	0	0	0	81	4.7	Accepted
New media gives broadcast content producers new revenue streams through pay-per-view services	64	17	0	0	0	81	4.7	Accepted
New media enables audience to be active participants rather than passive audience	75	6	0	0	0	81	4.9	Accepted
Through the new media, there is faster audience feedback	47	34	0	0	0	81	4.5	Accepted
New media gives room for personalised content delivery	67	14	0	0	0	81	4.8	Accepted
New media gives room for rapid content production and distribution	72	9	0	0	0	81	4.8	Accepted
New media gives room for interactive content creation and sharing	59	22	0	0	0	81	4.7	Accepted

It could be inferred from the data in Table 2 that the benefits of new media to broadcast content producers is multifaceted, enhancing production and dissemination of content in different aspects.

Table 3: Responses on the Challenges of New Media on Broadcast Content Production and Delivery

Option	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean Rating	Decision
Acquiring new media tools is very costly, thus negatively impacting on budgets and gains	26	25	18	5	7	81	3.7	Accepted
Rapid changes in technology such as introduction of AI and virtual reality present huge demands to broadcast content producers to constantly be attuned with these technological changes	17	31	13	9	11	81	3.4	Accepted
High competition for audience attention and adverts	37	21	6	4	13	81	3.7	Accepted
Too much of content to handle	20	26	10	16	9	81	3.3	Accepted
Changing audience preferences is also a challenge	57	17	3	1	3	81	4.3	Accepted
Issues with the integrity of content accessed on new media, copyright breach and piracy as well as misinformation issue	22	25	14	9	11	81	4.3	Accepted

It could be inferred that in spite of the importance of new media technology to media producers and distributors, it is also challenged by several issues.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study as showed in Figure 2 revealed the extent to which the respondents made use of new media on broadcast content production and delivery. The results indicated that the application of new media in content production and dissemination was very high. The finding suggests the importance of digital communication technology in the broadcast industry. The finding is in agreement with Saka, (2021) which states that ICT has played a meaningful role and function in the strengthening of news production through the years. The result also aligns with that of Osapkolor et al (2021), who concluded that information technology has a significant level of

influence on the operations of the media and that the media is now driven by technology which has no turning back.

In addition, the study found that they respondents made use of different types of new media in content production. These included Streaming services such as Netflix, social media like Facebook Live, podcasting, Internet Protocol Television and Over-the-Top-Platforms (see Table 1 above). The finding is in tandem with an earlier one by Wekesa et al (2025), which established that F, X, digital video cameras. YouTube, Live-U, SI media, Zoom apps, OB Tricasters, Skype and Smartphones have become useful communication tools in television production.

Finding of the study in Table 2 further revealed that new media presented opportunity to reach a wider audience with ease, it increased audience engagement, as well as new media allowed the integration of multimedia services. The finding also showed that new media gave broadcast content producers new revenue streams through pay-per-view services, it enabled audience to be active participants rather than passive audience, and through the new media, there was faster audience feedback. The study equally found that new media gave room for personalised content delivery, and for rapid content production and distribution, in addition to new media allowing for interactive content creation and sharing. The finding is a line with that of Imoh and Ifeanyi (2023), which established that the new media technology has significantly impacted the way broadcast contents are packaged and distributed. The study's finding is also in tandem with that of Lucas and Shalgan (2019), which uncovered that Information and Communication Technology, has widened the scope of newsgathering and reporting. The finding of justified the adoption of the Technological Determinism Theory, which states that, technology underpins all human endeavours. That is why broadcast content producers have taken advantage of the new media communication technology to enhance their content

Furthermore, the study's finding indicated that despite the importance of new media to broadcast content gathering and production, acquire new media tools is very costly, negatively impacting on budgets and gains. Fast pace of changes in technology like the AI innovation and virtual reality was a big challenge to broadcast content producers to constantly be attuned with these technological changes. Another finding was that there was high competition for audience attention and adverts, too much of content to handle, and changing audience preferences is also a challenge. Others were issues with the integrity of content accessed on new media, copyright breach and piracy, as well as misinformation issue. An earlier study by Olley's (2009) confirmed that while new media was having significant impact on the Nigeria broadcasting landscape such as improving gathering and dissemination of broadcast contents, it was challenged by high cost of new media gadgets purchase, network issues and electricity challenges. The study's finding also corroborated that Imoh and Ifeanyi (2023), which revealed that new media technology has increased competition in the broadcast industry and the challenges of meeting the needs of digital audience based on their individual characteristics.

Conclusion/ Recommendations

The study appraised broadcast content producers' perception of the challenges and benefits of new media in broadcast production. From the findings of the study, it was concluded that despite some

challenges with new media in broadcast content production, the news media has presented a huge benefits to broadcast contents producers. This was due to the fact that new media has supported the efficiency and efficacy of broadcast content generation and delivery, enhanced visualised broadcast content presentation, interaction with audience, as well as enhancing personalised broadcast content sensitivity in professional knowledge upgrade. Therefore, both private and public broadcast media owners in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria should increase their budget allocations especially as they concern the purchase of new media equipment and other aspects of production that requires the use of new media technologies such as data subscription.

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